

Imagination Lancaster researchers' response to UK Government consultation on copyright and artificial intelligence

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Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence

We are a group of researchers from Imagination Lancaster, a design research facility based at Lancaster University. For the past few years, our AI working group has been working on projects around artificial intelligence. Specifically, this has been in relation to small-medium enterprises and creative industries' perceptions and concerns around AI, crossing over into issues related to legibility such as copyright.

Question 4 of the consultation online survey asks whether we agree with option 3 (in relation to sections B.1 - B.4 of the consultation). There are assumptions built into these objectives and options. These include that increasing AI model training in the UK will increase overall value to the UK and that outputs of a model do not cause challenges to copyright from a reproduction point of view. We suggest these assumptions deserve further interrogation.

One current challenge is that current AI models do already rely on training data that invariably includes a large amount of copyrighted works. As a result, they output material that could be considered reproduction of copyrighted works (as per point 41 of the consultation document) beyond the temporary copies exemption (as per Question 26). Even though guardrails might be in place to attempt to prevent direct reproduction, emerging cases show that prompting models in certain ways can easily reproduce copyrighted works.¹ This can even happen without mention to the copyrighted work directly. If vast volumes of copyrighted works are used as input for the model it may be difficult, if not impossible, for a user to know if the output they are receiving is close enough to be considered (legally speaking) a reproduction of copyright work if they are unfamiliar with the source material. This is as much an issue for users of AI models as for creative producers whose work may have been used to train them. Additionally, the *Reuters vs ROSS* case² ruled out the defence of fair use in relation to copyrighted material

¹ Marcus, Gary & Southen, Reid. 2024. Generative AI Has a Visual Plagiarism Problem: Experiments with Midjourney and DALL-E 3 show a copyright minefield. *IEEE Spectrum*. Source: <https://spectrum.ieee.org/midjourney-copyright>

² Brittan, Blake. 2025. Thomson Reuters wins AI copyright 'fair use' ruling against one-time competitor. Reuters. Source: <https://www.reuters.com/legal/thomson-reuters-wins-ai-copyright-fair-use-ruling-against-one-time-competitor-2025-02-11/>

used in training data of an AI model, setting a precedent for future AI copyright related cases. We note that similar legal cases are being built in the UK.³

Option 3 suggests an opt-out model, where right holders must explicitly and pre-emptively state that they do not want their work to be used for data mining. Testimony from an AI expert in our research suggests that drawing in *“everything we’ve ever done [...] and then using that to make money [is not a] sustainable position”*⁴. Instead, they highlighted how *“new lines”* need to be drawn over how these models incorporate training data from across the web. This speaks to Question 12, and anxieties from creative organisations that current practices for licencing of content for AI are not meeting needs. Considering the opt-out model, it is also important to consider that the current generation of technology does not include any reasonable means to determine what (potentially copyrighted) data was used to train an AI model, making retroactive action challenging. If an opt-out model is adopted, it is crucial to establish what mechanisms rights holders can lean upon to insist that work that has already been incorporated into AI models either be removed or they are paid fair compensation for licencing this work. Such a mechanism should be reasonable and enforceable.

Evidence from our research suggests option 3 will create a large burden for creative practitioners, especially SMEs, who may not have the expertise or resources to undertake the proposed actions. This is something small to medium organisations are particularly concerned about, for example several participants in our AI summit event held in 2023 highlighted a need for clarity over AI and copyright and the nuances within this e.g., *“created content as well as generation and manipulation of existing material”*. One contributor to our research mentioned how a challenge for companies is *“overcoming the AI fatigue”* in relation to an overwhelming amount of information to process and understand AI advances. On one panel, a business owner explained they felt this advantages larger scale organisations, compared with SMEs e.g., how they only have *“a*

³ Baringslaw.com. 2024. Manchester Law Firm Takes on Microsoft and Google in European-First Action for Unauthorised Data Use. Source: <https://baringslaw.com/press-releases/manchester-law-firm-takes-on-microsoft-and-google-in-european-first-action-for-unauthorised-data-use/>

⁴ Laura Ellis, Head of Technology Forecasting, BBC as part of the panel from Imagination Lancaster’s AI Summit: Film and TV in conversation with Professor Paul Coulton, Professor of Speculative Game Design at Lancaster University & chaired by Dr Maryam Ghorbankarimi, Lecturer in Film Practice, Lancaster University. Source: <https://vimeo.com/showcase/10765269/video/880101095>

team of 6, we've just got to really flat out, just to get through the day"⁵, highlighting how they lack the time or space to understand AI and the impact to their organisation.

Therefore, we suggest that option 3 is inadequate. However, per question 8 we have our own suggestions about a way forward. For right holders to better reserve their rights we argue for an 'opt-in' rather than 'opt-out' approach. This is so creatives' work continues to be automatically protected by law, providing better control over how their work is used and allows them to explicitly consent to the use of their work for data mining.

Remuneration should be the default for using right holders' work, given that there must be a value in having this work; otherwise, AI companies would not need it. As set out in the consultation documents, this may result in smaller quantities of work being made available for training. However, we set out some suggestions below on how new forms of collective licensing would encourage creators to opt in.

Question 15 relates to collective licensing. We believe there may indeed be a role for the government in encouraging such schemes.

One form of this may be what is known as a blanket license, which would provide access to multiple works for a certain fee. This might be more feasible for creative industries where licensing individual works etc. might be too time consuming.

Right holders should be remunerated for their work being included in AI training models and this could provide an incentive for opting in. One existing process that could be looked at to provide a model for this fair compensation could be the Public Lending Right (PLR), whereby material placed in public libraries results in a small fee paid to the author each time it is taken out as a loan by a library user.

Another comparable model could be the Performing Rights Society (PRS) management of the rights to use music in public, whereby bars, clubs, public venues, etc all pay an annual licence fee for the right to use music in public, and then that money is divided up proportionally to all the artists who made that music. A similar scheme could function to provide microtaxation for the use of AI as a separate layer to specific remuneration for particular works, whereby every time an AI model is used it would incur a tax to be paid by

⁵ Andy Walmsley, Founder of Wash Studio & Co-Founder of The Artistry House as part of the panel from Imagination Lancaster's AI Summit: Provocation – Let's Panic panel. In discussion with chair Dr Joseph Lindley, Senior Research Fellow, Lancaster University. Source: <https://vimeo.com/showcase/10765269/video/880124605>

the operator (e.g. OpenAI) and used to compensate people who have a reasonable claim that their data have been included in training sets, and support original content creators.

Opt-in approaches can mirror the existing good practices in open-source sharing of creative and innovative work, as we observed for decades with Creative Commons (CC), the GNU General Public License (GPL), and other Free/Open Source Software (F/OSS) licenses. For instance, CC licenses come in different types, such as CC BY (Attribution), which requires users to give appropriate credit; CC BY-NC (Non-Commercial), which allows usage for non-commercial purposes only; and CC BY-SA (ShareAlike), which permits derivatives as long as they are distributed under the same license as the original. Similarly, the GPL ensures that users can use, modify, and distribute software, provided that any modified versions are also released under the GPL. Other F/OSS licenses like the MIT License and Apache License offer varying degrees of freedom and requirements. Such licensing schemes readily exist, offer varying degrees of protection for right holders, and creators are already familiar with these options. Mirroring these existing and familiar mechanisms will facilitate trust in creators in making informed choices about 'opting-in' for AI training.

We agree with the objective set out in point 54 that transparency is a vital part of any copyright framework with regards this context. One issue currently is that there is little transparency possible in terms of outputs of AI models, which may face technical constraints. Our response to question 17 is therefore that AI developers should disclose the sources of their training material. We suggest that above a certain scale it should be incumbent upon those training AI models to declare what the training data is, e.g., by giving filenames or attributions. This would give rights holders a practical 'right to reply' if they think their data has been included in a training set.

Overall, we strongly believe the best choice for right holders is to have an alternative opt-in model to better reserve their rights and protect the future of the creative industries. While advances in technology are important to support growth within the UK, as mentioned in the consultation, the UK creative industries are of vital importance to both our economy and innovation sector. Without this innovation, there would be no work to use within AI models and therefore right holders' needs should be the top priority within this process.

Signed by,

Kim Snooks, Naomi Jacobs, Joseph Lindley, Yekta Bakırlioğlu, Paul Coulton, Louise Mullagh, Glynn Stockton and Roger Whitham

Imagination Lancaster, Lancaster Institute for Contemporary Arts (LICA), Lancaster University

About the signatories

Kim Snooks is a Senior Research Associate at ImaginationLancaster, currently involved in the creation of a tool to help SMEs critically analyse their use of generative AI. Her work explores how design research can provoke debate around emerging technology futures including digital identities and self-tracking devices.

Naomi Jacobs is Lecturer in Design Policy and Futures Thinking at Lancaster University, researching technology and society, and the nature of digital public spaces. Much of her current research is related to how design research can be used in policymaking, particularly in the context of ensuring new technologies and digital platforms and services are ethical, transparent, trustworthy and respect privacy.

Joseph Lindley is a Senior Research Fellow at Lancaster University where he leads Design Research Works, a project whose aim is to show the world what it can gain from design research. He has a track record of publishing design-led research relating to adoption of AI technologies this include topics such as Design as a Rapid response methodology for AI, the practice of Prompt Craft, and AI legibility. He is a co-author of the IEEE P2840 standard for Responsible AI Licensing, co-authored the Arts and Humanities' Research Council's report on AI & Data, and in 2024 his AI-powered Shadowplay installation has been experienced by ~100,000 people.

Yekta Bakırlioğlu is a Senior Lecturer in Design Management at ImaginationLancaster and Postgraduate Director of Studies in Design at LICA. He is also a Trustee of Manchester Craft and Design Centre. His research focuses on open design, distributed production and design-led business models for sustainable, inclusive and democratic innovation.

Paul Coulton is Chair of Speculative and Game Design within Imagination Lancaster. His uses Speculative Design to combine real and/or hypothetical extrapolations of the development of emerging technologies with a consideration of the future worlds into which they may be deployed. His work helped establish Design Fiction, as a research method exploring mundane futures for areas such as the Internet of Things and Artificial intelligence. His current research focusses on More-Than-Human Design to expand design approaches to pay greater consideration to human and non-human actants within the complex assemblages particularly in relation to sustainability and climate change

Louise Mullagh is Lecturer in Arts Management. Her interdisciplinary research and teaching spans Critical Data Studies, digital curation, and participatory design, with a particular focus on how AI and emerging technologies are reshaping cultural institutions and governance. She has used design fiction and speculative methods to engage policymakers in rethinking data-driven decision-making.

Glynn Stockton is an International Lecturer in Design, Director of Studies for Design at LUC@BJTU and LICA Academic Integrity Officer. He also founded the Lancaster University Academic Integrity Officer Network and his research is principally focussed on the implications of GenAI on Academic Integrity and the broader issues affecting Academic Integrity within Higher Education.

Roger Whitham is a designer, researcher and educator based at ImaginationLancaster, Lancaster University. His research centres on collaborative interactions that span distinct contexts, technologies, sectors and scales; explored through co-design, tools and visualisation.

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